

Blast incidence in relation to nitrogen management through the leaf color chart

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Blast caused by *Magnaporthe grisea* (Hebert) Barr is an important disease in rice. Nitrogen plays a crucial role in the development of blast. Many experiments have shown that a high N supply induces heavy blast incidence, regardless of the phosphorus or potassium supply (Ou 1985). However, the severity of the disease varies with the method of N fertilizer application (Ou 1985). Hence, an experiment was conducted to evaluate the effect of N management through the leaf color chart (LCC) on blast incidence and rice productivity.

Field trials were conducted under rainfed conditions at ARS during the 1998 and 1999 wet seasons. Sowing was done on 10 June 1998 and harvest on 30 Oct 1998. P and K were applied at 22 and 41.5 kg ha⁻¹ as single superphosphate and muriate of potash. An entire dose was applied during sowing. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with 12 treatments and 4 replications. The two varieties—Abhilash (moderately blast-resistant) and Intan (blast-susceptible)—were the main-plot treatments. Subplot treatments consisted of N management based on critical LCC readings of 2.0, 2.75, 3.5, 4.25, and 5.0 in addition to the recommended practice of applying N in three equal splits at 20 and 40 d after emergence (DAE) and just before panicle initiation. In treatments with N management based on the LCC, the quantity of N applied each time during early growth (21–28 DAE), rapid

growth (35–49 DAE), and late growth (56 DAE to flowering) stages was 20, 30, and 20 kg ha⁻¹, respectively. Table 1 shows the total quantity of N applied in each treatment.

A 0–9 scale was used for scoring leaf blast, with a total of 15 leaves scored for each treatment from five plants. Percent disease index (PDI) was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{PDI} = \frac{\text{Sum of individual ratings}}{\text{No. of leaves assessed} \times \text{maximum disease grade}} \times 100$$

Percent neck blast was calculated by counting the number of panicles with typical blast symptoms in one square area.

$$\text{Percent neck blast} = \frac{\text{No. of infected panicles}}{\text{Total panicles no.}} \times 100$$

Results indicated that leaf blast incidence was significantly higher in Intan than in Abhilash at all N levels. In moderately resistant Abhilash, leaf blast incidence with the recommended practice was on a par with a critical LCC value of 3.5 during 1998. During 1999, Abhilash was free from leaf blast incidence at all N

levels. In susceptible Intan, leaf blast incidence at a critical LCC value of 3.5 (with 170 kg total N ha⁻¹) was significantly less than with the recommended practice (100 kg N ha⁻¹) in 1998 but statistically the same in 1999 (Table 2).

Neck blast incidence was also significantly more in Intan than in Abhilash. Different N application levels did not have any significant effect on neck blast incidence in Abhilash in 1999. In

Intan, neck blast incidence under the recommended N practice was on a par with the critical LCC values of 3.5 and 4.25 (Table 2). In terms of grain yield, Abhilash responded to N management based on the LCC up to the critical value of 4.25. However, Intan responded only up to the critical value of 3.5, with a total N appli-

Table 1. Total quantity of N applied (kg ha⁻¹) in different treatments.

Variety	Leaf color chart value					Recommended practice
	2.0	2.75	3.5	4.25	5.0	
1998						
Abhilash	0	40	110	230	270	100
Intan	0	0	170	250	270	100
1999						
Abhilash	0	30	70	150	210	100
Intan	0	40	70	140	210	100

Table 2. Percent blast disease index (PDI) and percent neck blast incidence (%).^a

Variety	Leaf color chart value (%) ^b					Recommended practice	Mean
	2.0	2.75	3.5	4.25	5.0		
<i>Leaf blast incidence</i>							
1998							
Abhilash	12.7 b x	15.2 b wx	17.4 b w	21.4 b v	23.3 b v	17.1 b w	17.9 b
Intan	30.6 a w	31.9 a w	34.0 a w	39.7 a v	42.1 a v	39.3 a v	36.3 a
Mean	21.6 y	23.6 wx	25.7 x	30.5 v w	32.7 v	28.2 y	
1999							
Intan	17.5 y	20.8 xy	21.4 wx	24.4 w	30.1 v	23.3 wx	
Abhilash	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Neck blast incidence</i>							
1998							
Abhilash	16.1 b y	21.7 b x	27.4 b w	29.2 b w	34.8 b v	28.0 b w	26.2 b
Intan	22.5 a y	29.2 a x	34.0 a w	36.3 a w	40.7 a v	36.4 a w	32.2 a
Mean	19.3 y	25.5 x	30.8 w	32.8 w	37.7 v	32.2 w	
1999							
Abhilash	18.0 a v	20.5 a v	21.2 b v	21.4 b v	21.5 b v	20.6 b v	20.6 b
Intan	18.0 a z	21.6 a yz	25.0 a xy	32.2 a vw	37.0 a v	27.4 a xy	27.0 a
Mean	18.0 y	21.1 xy	23.2 x	26.8 vw	29.3 v	24.8 wx	

^aDuncan's multiple range test (DMRT at 5%) was used to compare treatment means. ^bRows/columns followed by the same letters do not differ significantly; comparison of means in a row is indicated by a to e and comparison of means in a column by v to z.

Table 3. Grain yield (t ha⁻¹), 1998.^a

Variety	Leaf color chart treatment ^b					Recommended practice	Mean
	2.0	2.75	3.5	4.25	5.0		
Abhilash	c	c	b	a	a	bc	4.2 a
	3.3 a x	3.1 a x	4.3 a w	5.2 a v	5.5 a v	4.0 a wx	
Intan	b	b	a	b	b	b	3.0 a
	2.9 a w	2.9 a w	4.4 a v	2.5 b w	2.2 b w	2.8 a w	
Mean	3.1 w	3.0 w	4.4 v	3.9 vw	3.8 vw	3.4 w	

^aDuncan's multiple range test (DMRT) at 5% was used to compare treatment means. ^bRows/columns followed by the same letters do not differ significantly.

cation of 170 kg ha⁻¹. Grain yields in these treatments were significantly higher than those under recommended N management (Table 3).

Results indicated that N application based on an LCC value of 3.5 helped to manage blast more effectively in a susceptible variety (Intan) compared with the recommended practice of N application. Rice productivity can be increased by higher N application based on the LCC reading. The critical LCC value for N management varied between the two varieties.

Reference

Ou SH. 1985. Rice disease. 2d ed. Kew (England): Commonwealth Agricultural Bureau. 380 p.

Water and weed management studies in direct-seeded upland rice

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Direct-seeded upland rice is an important system of rice culture occupying almost 22% of the total rice area in India. In Assam, this crop is locally known as *ahu* rice (Mar/Apr–Jun/July). Assam farmers prefer this crop because this period is characterized by low rainfall, clear skies, and low frequency of floods. However, some constraints limit the widespread cultivation of *ahu* rice:

uncertain rainfall; high evaporative demand, causing moisture stress; and weed infestation. Although the application of irrigation can solve the problem of moisture stress, scheduling of irrigation in upland situations where seed is sown in dry unpuddled soil is very difficult. Hence, upland rice should have drought tolerance to withstand possible moisture stress in be-

tween irrigation schedules. Seed hardening with potassium salt before sowing helps induce drought tolerance in crops (Chinoy et al 1970).

This study was carried out to assess the performance of upland rice under seed treatment and water and weed management practices. The experiment was conducted at AAU during the 1991 summer (Mar-Jul) in a